

Informative Paper

COMPAS_sCO₂

NEW CHROMIUM ALLOYS DEVELOPMENT FOR FUTURE APPLICATIONS IN CONCENTRATING SOLAR POWER TECHNOLOGIES

Third informative paper

INTRODUCTION

The 4.5-year EU Horizon 2020 project COMPASsCO₂ is approaching to its end. As all Research and Innovation Actions (RIA) projects its aim is to shape future energy systems that are more sustainable, cost competitive and that can foster the development of a low-carbon industry value chain in the European continent.

Concentrating solar thermal (CST) is a relatively old and established technology; however, its potential for large-scale development is held back by a series of barriers that must be promptly addressed to reach the decarbonisation of energy system goal.

During the project implementation a series of major innovations that can lead to a CST renaissance have been investigated and reported. In addition to technical deliverables and scientific publications, wider audience-oriented papers have been produced to disseminate findings in a more narrative way in order to increase awareness on sustainable energy technologies and highlight the efforts of both research and industry for the transition to a carbon neutral energy mix in Europe, in line with the Net-Zero Industry Act. In the first informative paper (COMPASsCO₂, 2023), the design of new heat-transfer particles that can withstand high temperatures and are abrasion-resistant was addressed. The second informative paper (COMPASsCO₂, 2024) summarised the main research on the evaluation of metal alloys for heat exchanger tubes, and the investigation of their properties under the harsh conditions of the application selected. This third paper focuses more specifically on chromium-based alloys and their potential for application in future CST systems.

The development of advanced materials is critical to the next generation of CST technologies, particularly for heat exchangers operating in extreme environments, not only for electricity generation but also for the provision of process heat at high temperature. Chromium-based alloys, including nickel aluminide (Cr-NiAl in the following) and silicide (Cr-Si) variants, present promising solutions due to their high-temperature stability, oxidation resistance, and improved mechanical properties.

STATE-OF-THE-ART AND COMPAS_sCO₂ CONTRIBUTION

The design of a heat exchanger to operate at high temperature (>700 °C), high pressure (>25 MPa), corrosive and high wear environment presents significant challenges for current state-of-the-art advanced austenitic stainless steels and nickel (Ni) superalloys. Therefore, research is concentrating on more suitable materials. Chromium metals were investigated in the 1950-60s for application in the aerospace industry. They present highly desirable characteristics owing to their higher melting points (T_m), low cost, lower mass density (Table 1), good thermal conductivity and high temperature oxidation resistance. However, they exhibit a Ductile to Brittle Transition Temperature (DBTT, typically around $0.15 T_m$) meaning they are typically brittle at room temperature. This drawback is reported to depend strongly on its purity and, together with the increased attention into nickel-based superalloys lead to the demise of scientific interest into Chromium-based alloys until recently. In the framework of COMPASsCO₂, chromium-based alloys have been evaluated as candidate material in the development of next generation CST, with the goals to: (1) Increase operating temperature capability – enabling improved thermodynamic efficiencies and extension of operation lifetime, and (2) Withstand abrasion of particles. State of the art materials have been compared against two newly developed Cr superalloys which, respectively, add NiAl precipitates and advanced Cr alloys reinforced with Cr₃Si. Cr aluminides and silicides offer significant prospects for simultaneous improvements in both high temperature strength and abrasion resistance as bulk monolithic materials. However, they were explored also as coating and surface modifications applied to traditional steel and Ni materials in order to improve their resistance to oxidation,

corrosion and erosion. In the following, the main research steps and results are provided for both Cr-NiAl and Cr-Si categories. In addition, results of the work conducted on Cr-Si diffusion coatings are briefly presented.

Table 1: Density and melting point (T_m) of elements and Ni-superalloy CMSX-4 (source: COMPASsCO₂ D3.1, November 2022)

Element	Density (g cm ⁻³)	Melting Point (°C)	Thermal conductivity (W/m K)
Cr	7.14 (8,10)	1890 (8,11,12)	93.7 (13)
Ni	8.9 (2)	1453 (14)	90.7 (13)
Al	2.7 (15)	660 (14)	237 (13)
Fe	7.87 (15)	1535 (14)	80.2 (13)
Co	8.85 (12)	1495 (14)	99.2 (13)
CMSX-4	8.7(16)	1396 (17)	10 (18)

I. Cr-NiAl Alloys

Chromium-Nickel-Aluminium (Cr-NiAl) alloys have been investigated for their superior thermal stability and mechanical strength. The incorporation of nickel aluminide precipitates into a chromium matrix helps overcoming several limitations by enhancing precipitation hardening, improving creep resistance and strength at high temperatures. The main research focus was to:

- Demonstrate the alloy design in Cr-NiAl alloys with Fe addition to enhance precipitate volume fraction;
- Determine microstructure stability which corresponds to the coarsening rate of the NiAl precipitate of Cr superalloys;
- Investigate the mechanical properties of Cr-superalloys at room temperature.

WP3 followed a structured approach, integrating literature review, theoretical modelling, alloy fabrication, characterization, and performance testing.

CALculation of PHase Diagram (CALPHAD) was employed for initial composition selection. The ternary phase diagram of Cr-Ni-Al was analysed at 1200 °C and 1400 °C under atmospheric pressure using the TCNI-8 database. Pseudo-binary Cr-NiAl(-Fe) was investigated while fixing the amount of Fe in the system to ensure the ageing temperature would remain in a single-phase region.

High-purity elements were arc-melted under an inert argon atmosphere to produce ingots. Samples underwent homogenization at 1400 °C for 20 hours to achieve chemical uniformity. Aging treatments at 800 °C, 1000 °C, and 1200 °C were applied to control precipitate formation and coarsening.

Microstructural Analysis conducted via Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Atom Probe Tomography (APT) reveals a coherent NiAl phase within the Cr matrix, contributing to improved mechanical stability.

Hardness measurements using a 500 g load a Vickers microhardness tester demonstrates that the Cr-10Ni-10Al-20Fe composition exhibits superior mechanical performance compared to ternary Cr-NiAl alloys due to fine precipitate dispersion and solid solution strengthening.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) confirmed lower oxidation rates compared to conventional Ni-based superalloys, making these alloys suitable for high-temperature applications. The addition of Fe enhanced NiAl solubility in the Cr matrix, refining the distribution of strengthening precipitates. Moreover, the addition of iron reduces temperature of maximum solubility from 1400° C to 1300° C.

As far as oxidation resistance is concerned, Cr-NiAl alloys showed significantly lower weight gain in oxidation tests compared to traditional Ni-based superalloys, confirming their potential for high-temperature applications. Still, the oxide scale has to be further analysed for a firm conclusion and oxidation resistance needs to be improved, for instance by adding Si as demonstrated in Cr-Cr₃Si alloys below.

Ductility remained a challenge at lower temperatures, but creep resistance was improved by optimizing aging treatments.

Figure 1 : Cr-10Ni-10Al (left) and Cr-10Ni-10Al-20Fe homogenised at 1400 °C for 20 hr (right) showing the increased solubility of NiAl with additions of Fe (source: COMPASSCO₂ D3.1)

Figure 2 : Coarsening rate for Cr-superalloys (Cr-5Ni-5Al, Cr-10Ni-10Al, Cr-5Ni-5Al-10Fe, and Cr-10Ni-10Al-20Fe); Ni-superalloys (CMSX-2 Series A (35), IN939 Cast HT1 (33), Ni-10Cr-9Co (31)); and Fe-superalloys (Fe-10Ni-15Al (36), Fe-12Ni-12V (34), Fe-12Ni-9V-3Ti (32)) (source: COMPASSCO₂ D3.1)

Figure 3 : Vickers hardness (HV0.5) of the Cr(Fe)-Ni-Al alloys under different heat-treatment conditions and aging at 800/1000/1200 °C for 4/20/100/240 hours measured at room temperature. (source: COMPASsCO₂ D3.1)

II. New Cr silicides

The focus was on optimizing the synthesis of chromium silicides, ensuring reproducibility and scalability for industrial applications. Various samples with different compositions were produced by arc melting, which are shown in Table 2. To be able to determine the influence of alloying by Fe and Ni, the Si amount was held constant at 8 at.%, while Cr and the alloying element were varied systematically. Two different alloy compositions (Cr-Si-Fe, Cr-Si-Ni) were explored, leveraging state-of-the-art powder metallurgy and casting techniques to achieve high purity and uniformity. The fabrication process included advanced sintering and heat treatment procedures to enhance microstructural stability. Coupons of these novel materials were successfully fabricated, demonstrating promising microstructural characteristics.

Table 2: Compositions of produced alloys (at.%) (source: COMPASsCO₂ D3.2, November 2022)

Cr-Si-Fe	90-8-2	88-8-4	86-8-6	84-8-8	76-8-8	60-8-32
Cr-Si-Ni	90-8-2	88-8-4	86-8-6	84-8-8	76-8-8	60-8-32

Detailed Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and X-ray Diffraction (XRD) analyses confirmed the formation of targeted chromium silicide phases. The microstructure displayed uniform grain distribution and minimal porosity, ensuring high material integrity.

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) tests were conducted to assess oxidation kinetics and phase stability at high temperatures. The results indicate superior oxidation resistance compared to conventional high-temperature alloys, with the formation of a protective SiO₂ layer that mitigates material degradation.

Hardness and fracture toughness measurements were performed using Vickers hardness testing and indentation fracture toughness methods. The results demonstrated significantly higher hardness values than traditional Cr-based alloys, alongside improved crack propagation resistance.

Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) and Electron Probe Microanalysis (EPMA) confirmed the homogeneous distribution of elements, with no unwanted phase formations or chemical segregation, which is critical for long-term performance stability.

To determine the DBTT of the alloys, compression tests at various temperature levels (400°C, 500°C, 600°C and 700°C for Cr-Si-Fe and at 700°C and 800°C for Cr-Si-Ni) were conducted. Figure 4 and 5 below report the compressive fracture percent deformation for the different temperatures. For each temperature a representative fractured sample is shown.

Figure 4 : Results of compression tests conducted at different temperatures for the Cr-Si-Fe alloys: Fracture compression and fracture patterns of the alloys in dependence of the testing temperatures. (source: COMPASsCO₂ D3.2)

Figure 4 shows that for the samples fractured at 400°C, 500°C and 600°C no significant increase in deformation occurred and all samples showed a fracture pattern which can be considered as brittle. In contrast, samples of all alloy compositions at 700°C did not fracture at all and showed a very ductile behaviour. It can be concluded that the DBTT for the tested alloys is somewhere in the temperature range between 600°C and 700°C. Accordingly, alloying with Fe does not seem to have a major influence on the DBTT.

Figure 5 : Results of compression tests conducted at different temperatures for the Cr-Si-Ni alloys: Fracture compression and fracture patterns of the alloys as a function of the testing temperatures (source: COMPASsCO₂ D3.2)

Compared to the Cr-Si-Fe alloys, where all samples show very ductile behaviour at 700°C, the samples of the Cr-Si-Ni alloys still demonstrate brittle fracture at 700°C. At 800°C the Cr₈₈Si₈Ni₄ sample does not fracture and shows very high deformation. According to this, the DBTT can be estimated to be between 700°C and 800°C. However, the Cr₈₆Si₈Ni₆ sample fractures even at 800°C in a somewhat brittle manner and it is possible that the DBTT was not reached. It can be concluded that alloying with higher amounts of Ni seems to embrittle the alloys and increases the DBTT. Balancing silicide volume fraction with matrix ductility is a key objective. Hardness and durability of Cr-Si-Fe and Cr-Si-Ni alloys make them suitable for use as coatings for conventional Fe/Ni substrates. This investigation is described in the following section.

III. Cr-Si slurry coatings

A novel slurry coating technique has been developed for application on steels and nickel-based superalloys. The advantage of this process compared to traditional pack cementation is that slurry-based coatings do not require embedding into and heating of a big powder bed, nor large furnaces (as more localized heat treatments can be used), and are thus a much more economical option, especially for the dimensions of the targeted heat exchanger tubes. The desired elements for a slurry coating are in the form of metallic powders and are mixed with a binder to form a slurry. The slurry is deposited on the material surface by dipping, brushing or spraying. The diffusion coating is then formed during a subsequent heat treatment by interdiffusion between the metallic particles from the slurry and the substrate.

The main challenge during the development process was to determine the right slurry composition and heat treatment parameters to obtain a dense diffusion layer.

The investigated substrates for the Cr-Si slurry diffusion coating include P92 (ferritic steel), Sanicro 25 (austenitic steel) and Inconel 740 (Ni-based superalloy). The conducted investigations included phase analysis by SEM, XRD and EPMA for the various coatings, as well as hardness measurements. For all of these coatings a dense diffusion layer with a thickness of >50 μm was observed. In order to assess the suitability and resistance of the coatings within the targeted heat exchanger environment, samples were produced for corrosion, erosion and oxidation tests.

Figure 6 : Cross-section of the Cr-Si-slurry coating on P92, Sanicro25 and Inconel 617b, applied with a slurry composition of Cr-Si- and results of microhardness measurements (source: COMPASsCO₂ D3.3)

NEXT STEPS AND CONCLUSIONS

State of the art materials have been compared against two newly developed Cr superalloys which, respectively, add NiAl precipitates and advanced Cr alloys reinforced with Cr₃Si silicides.

As far as the first material category is concerned, after investigating the solubilities, coarsening rates and hardness of ternary and quaternary Cr-NiAl(-Fe) systems the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The design of Cr-NiAl alloys with Fe additions is validated by CALPHAD calculation and experiment. The addition of Fe increases the solubility of the NiAl phase which avoids the dendritic and eutectic precipitates and allows a higher volume fraction of precipitate compared to the ternary alloys. Fe, Ni and Al in solid solution with Cr increases the hardness of the matrix by solid solution strengthening.
- Cr-NiAl has an improved coarsening resistance over ferritic superalloys and Ni-superalloys at high temperatures. The presence of NiAl precipitate leads to substantial precipitate strengthening over pure chromium.
- Cr-NiAl alloys show improved oxidation resistance compared to pure Cr but bear similar oxidation kinetics. Fe addition show minor effect on the oxidation kinetics of Cr-NiAl.

A novel slurry-based Cr-Si diffusion coating process was developed, resulting in higher durability with enhanced resistance to oxidation and erosion at higher temperatures.

However, some challenges still remain for industrial application, of which the still limited thermal cycling resilience is a major aspect. The development of advanced chromium silicides

also represented a significant step into a deeper learning about material properties in high-temperature applications and the identification of suitable components ensuring exceptional thermal and oxidation resistance. The successful production of chromium silicide coupons marks a crucial milestone and could pave the way for broader industrial adoption, particularly in aerospace, energy, and other high-temperature applications where materials must withstand harsh environments. In the final stages of the project, research focused on assessing the performance of this novel material class under high temperature exposure in both synthetic air and CO₂ environments. Final project results and main takeaways were presented at the COMPASsCO₂ event **“Back to the Future: A Forward-Thinking Approach to Concentrating Solar Technologies”** held at CVR premises on 24 April 2025. Planned future efforts will focus on: i) further optimisation of chemical composition to enhance material ductility; ii) conducting long-term creep and thermal cycling tests, iii) scaling up production to assess industrial feasibility and iv) validating cost-effective production of these new materials.

The project COMPASsCO₂ provides the path for advancing future commercial CST power plants utilizing s-CO₂ Brayton cycle technologies through the development of novel materials and components specifically designed for the linkage of a solar tower including thermal storage with the power cycle via a particles/s-CO₂ heat exchanger. This requires the joint research effort of CST and material researchers as well as industrial components manufacturer specialists.

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ABOUT COMPAS_sCO₂

COMPAS_sCO₂ aims to integrate CSP particle systems into highly efficient s-CO₂ Brayton power cycles for electricity production. Its research focus is on three main technological improvements:

- **development of new particles**

In order for particles to meet high temperatures new ceramic particles with improved performance will be developed and tested under relevant conditions

- **development of new metal alloys**

Answers about how the processing and combination with substrate steels will affect the microstructure, phase composition and also chemical stability of the newly developed materials will be provided. Modelling the degradation progress over time to estimate the lifetime of the new materials and coatings under different conditions will be performed.

- **development of the heat exchanger section**

To validate the interaction between the developed particles and the new structural materials in a relevant environment, the project includes the design, construction and testing of a heat exchanger section. Parameters relevant for the lifetime, like attrition rates, and performance parameters, like heat transfer, on the tube and first operating experiences are generated in a relevant heat exchanger environment.

In addition to the research component, COMPAS_sCO₂ includes a **communication and dissemination package for a wide range of stakeholders**. This Horizon 2020 project has a four-year duration (2020-2024) and is coordinated by DLR, with 12 European partners.

For more information

Check the project's website: www.compassco2.eu

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